

Transition and Adjustment of First-Year Student College in Dormitory: A Literature Review

Mukhroni¹, Sowiyah Sowiyah², Hasan Hariri³

¹Student Master of Educational Administration, Universitas Lampung

^{2,3}Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Lampung

ABSTRACT: The importance of transition and adjustment of students in the first year is interesting to study, and this paper examines the role of campus dormitories in assisting first year students in their transition and adjustment. There are several articles on reviews of transitions and adjustment of first-year students to be found. The purpose of this review is to find out the role of dormitories in the transition and adjustment period of first year students. Based on the results of a literature review, we found that campus dormitories can help students in transitioning and adjusting to their first year.

KEYWORDS: Adjustment, College, Dormitory, First-Year Student, Transition

INTRODUCTION

Transition and adjustment from high school to college is a complex process for almost all students in their first-year college. Transition is described as a "cultural shock involving significant social and psychological re-learning in the face of encounters with new ideas, new teachers and friends with sufficiently varied values and beliefs, new freedom and opportunities, and new academic, personal and social demands" [23]. Life transition, such as moving from home to college, create valuable opportunities for growth and change while also potentially increasing self-doubt and disappointment, and even encouraging self-defeating habits [10].

Entering college marks an important transition for many students. Entering college requires students to face many transitions, including changes in their life, academic environment, social environment, and adapting to their independence and responsibilities. Although many make this transition to college successfully, others experience long-term emotional mismatch and depression [19]. University as a place of learning is a place with great opportunities for students to develop their identity, morals and science. However, like any major life event, it too was accompanied by many significant changes. For example, supervision and protection of parents and teachers decreased, daily routines were changed, and individuals had to face challenges in academia, social relations, and other areas demanded by the new environment. As a result, the prevalence of adjustment disorder is relatively high among college students, especially in first and second year students [26]. Adjustment to college involves a variety of demands differing in kind and degree and requiring lot of coping responses or adjustments [23]. Because adjustment reflects the association between the individual and the environment, it is necessary to understand the transition, and adjustment to it, by examining characteristics of the environment and individuals endeavors to adjust within it [26].

During the transition period, first-year students will learn a new social life so that they are required to make adjustments and social adjustments. Students' ability to adapt during the first year of college can provide the basis for their adaptability to subsequent events during their life in college [7]. Previous research has suggested that students in their first-year face more difficulties in adjusting academically [23], if students are able to adapt themselves academically well, then all their abilities will adjust to the college environment [7]. Based on the results of these reviews, adjustment is the most important thing for students in their first-year of study.

In other research, [32] shows the role of parenting and current relationships with parents, in relation to psychological well-being variables, on student adjustment in university. However, what about the transition and adjustment of students who have to be far from their parents or live in a dormitory? There are still few studies on the transition period and adjustment of first-year students in college dormitories, so it is necessary to conduct research on how the transition and adjustment period of first-year students in college dormitories is necessary.

Dormitory as places for students to rest, study and interact play a very important role in student growth and development. Dormitories are the closest environment that can directly have a big influence on student development, with the programs offered in them, educational programs can directly influence the development of students, both in personality, academic abilities, and the development

of potential interests and talents of students [18]. Better dorm life can provide a sense of security and comfort for students so that they are better equipped to commit to academic studies and other more challenging assignments [5]. Based on this description, researchers are interested in exploring further about the role of dormitories in the transition and adjustment period of first-year students in college.

METHOD

This literature review focuses on the relationship between transition, first-year student adjustment, and college dormitory. The integrative review methodology was used to allow the inclusion of a wide variety of theoretical and empirical literature [25]. The review process draws from relevant literature using a transparent and reproducible search method, and the data obtained is analyzed and synthesized [29]. The review process began with a search engine, Google scholar, to search for articles with keywords: “transition, first-year student adjustment, and college dormitory”. The search ranged was from 2000-2020 and it is identified a total of 17.300 studies and articles.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Study Type

The research design adopted in this scientific research is quantitative and qualitative methods.

2. Type of Intervention

The main intervention examined in scientific research is transition and adjustment first-year students.

Journals that match the inclusion criteria and have the theme of transition, adjustment and dormitory, for later review.

The criteria for the journals selected for review are journals in which there is a theme of transition, adjustment and dormitory.

The inclusion criteria for this article are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Dormitory	Barracks
Adjustment	Workers dormitory
Transition	Different racial/ethnic
First-year of university	Boarding student
High school to college	Dissertations and theses
College/university	

Table 2. The results of the literature study table that was researched

No	Title	Author(s) and year	Type of Organization	N	Country	Method	Result
1	The Effect of Friends' Social Support on New Students' Social Adjustment in College Environment	Estiane (2015) [7]	University	203 students	Indonesian	Quantitative	There is the influence of social support from friends on the social adjustment of new students in the college environment.
2	University Belonging, Friendship Quality, and Psychological Adjustment During the Transition to College	Pittman and Richmond (2008) [19]	University	79 Students	USA	Quantitative	The sense of university ownership and quality of friendship were important factors in the adjustment of students to college during the first-year.

3	First-Year Students' Adjustment to University Life as Function of Relationships With Parents	Wintre and Yaffe (2000) [32]	University	408 first-year students	Canada, North America	Quantitative	The psychological well-being had an influence on the adjustment of first-year students at university.
4	Adjustment and Emotion Maturity Among First-year College Student	Sharma (2012) [23]	University	100 students	India	Quantitative and qualitative	The First-year students are not mature enough emotional and thus face difficulty in adjusting emotions with changing environmental demands compared to final year students.
5	Social Support : Relations to Coping and Adjustment During the Transition to University in the People's Republic of China	Tao, Dong et al. (2000) [26]	University	106 students	China	Quantitative	that overall social support at the start of the first semester is associated with adjustments at the end of the first semester either on a basis directly or indirectly through less negative coping patterns and more positive coping in among those who reported greater perceived social support
6	Consultation, Contribution, and Shared Benefits-The Golden Principle of Creating a Better Dormitory Life for College Student	Dan-Ping (2018) [5]	University		China	Descriptive	In order to create a better dorm life, students must first raise awareness of "Broad Consultation", and then increase the "contribution" mechanism.
7	High School to College Transition : A Profile of the Stressors, Physical and Psychological Health Issues That Affect the First-Year On-Campus College Student	Hicks and Heastie (2008) [10]	University	514 students	North Carolina	Quantitative	The first-year freshmen may have adjustment problems and experience unwanted stress and psychological problems during the first-year on campus

8	Behavioral Risks during the Transition from High School to College	Fromme, Corbin et al. (2008) [9]	University	2210 students	Southwest United States	Quantitative	Behavior changes during the transition period, especially during the first-year of college, are due to decreased adult supervision and freedom to live outside the home. Colleges may also consider policies that promote greater supervision in dormitories
9	Estimating the effects of dormitory living on student performance	Murray and Arajao (2010) [15]	University	363 students	USA	Quantitative	There is an increase in the achievement of GPA for students living in dormitories.
10	Relationship between Coping and University Adjustment and Academic Achievement amongst First-year Undergraduates in a Malaysian Public University	Abdullah, Elias et al. (2010) [1]	University	250 students	Malaysia	Quantitative	The findings of this study indicate that there is a significant and positive relationship between student coping with overall university adjustment, academic adjustment, social adjustment, personal-emotional adjustment, student engagement with university, and academic achievement.
11	Social Support, Self-Esteem, and Stress as Predictors of Adjustment to University Among First-Year Undergraduates	Friedlander, Reid et al. (2007) [8]	University	115 students	Canada, North America	Quantitative	Consistently self-perceived stress changes be a major predictor of adjustment. Social support is an important protective factor assist students in making the transition to university
12	Formation of Socio-Academic Climate in Student Dormitory	Utari, Sutapa et al. (2014) [31]	University	132 students	Indonesian	Quantitative	Creates a socio-academic climate can be identified aspects that are components in the development of the social academic climate in student flats, that is: a) occupant aspects, b)

							aspects nanny, c) aspects of the development system, d) aspects of the facility, and e) organizational aspects
13	Achievement Motivation and Self-Efficacy in Relation to Adjustment among University Students	Elias, Noordin et al. (2010) [6]	University	178 students	Malaysia	Quantitative	The students with high achievement motivation tend to be confident, responsible and have positive beliefs in themselves
14	Coping Styles, Social Support, Relational Self-Constraint, and Resilience in Predicting Students' Adjustment to University Life	Rahat and İlhan (2016) [20]	University	527 students	Turkey	Quantitative	The optimism in freshmen was one of the factors that facilitated the adjustment process to university life. The coping styles were the most effective predictors of personal adjustment from among all subdimensions of adjustment to university life, and social support sources were the most effective predictors of social adjustment.
15	Transitioning From High School to College: Relations of Social Support, Ego-Resiliency, and Maladjustment During Emerging Adulthood	Taylor, Doane et al. (2014) [27]	University	(Ns = 82, 76, and 71 at Times 1, 2, and 3, respectively)	USA	Quantitative	Internalizing symptoms were concurrently negatively correlated with perceived social support from friends and family as well as with ego-resiliency, and ego-resiliency was positively, concurrently correlated with perceived social support from friends.
16	Homesickness and Adjustment in University Students	Thurber and Walton (2012) [28]	University	500 female students	USA	Quantitative	A comprehensive school-based anti-homesickness program that customized each of the prevention and treatment recommendations above would likely see

							a dramatic reduction in the prevalence and intensity of homesickness on campus.
17	The effectiveness of solution-focused brief therapy on increasing social adjustment of female students residing in Tehran University dormitories	Saffarpour , Farahbakhsh et al. (2011) [22]	University	500 female students as sample	Iran	Quantitative	After participating in sessions led by a therapist, they will find possible solutions for the social problems they have faced, in relating to their new environment and being away from their family.
18	Living–Learning Programs And First-Generation College Students’ Academic And Social Transition To To College	Inkelas, Daver et al. (2007) [12]	University	33 campuses who had first-generation respondents	Colombia	Quantitative	First-generation L/L program students had a statistically significant higher mean score on perceptions of ease with their academic transition to college
19	Identity Status, Identity Processing Style, and the Transition to University	Berzonsky and Kuk (2000) [2]	University	363 students	USA	Quantitative	The present results suggest that students’ levels of personal identity development may play a role in the extent to which they experience difficulty and problems in making the transition to university.
20	The Impact of Residence Design on Freshman Outcomes: Dormitories Versus Suite-Style Residences	Rodger and Johnson (2005) [21]	University	909 students (159 students living in suite-style accommodations, and 750 students living in dormstyle accommodations)	Canada, North America	Quantitative	The demonstration that students living in suite-style residences report a significantly higher sense of belonging. Furthermore, students living in suite-style buildings demonstrate a significantly higher activity level than their peers living in dorm-style residences.

21	Predicting Transition And Adjustment To College: Biomedical And Behavioral Science Aspirants' And Minority Students' First Year Of College	Hurtado, Han et al. (2007) [11]	University	sample of 5049 students comprised of URM science majors (1851), White/Asian science majors (1366), and URM nonscience majors (1832)	USA	Quantitative	this study confirms that academic adjustment and sense of belonging are strongly linked for all students in the first year of college
22	First Year Students' Engagement at the University	Mehdinezhad (2011) [13]	University	551 students	Iran	Quantitative	The highest correlation is related to the online engagement scale with the intellectual engagement, the transition engagement with the student-staff engagement, peer engagement scale with the academic engagement, and the beyond-class engagement scale with the online engagement.
23	The Importance of Friends Friendship and Adjustment Among 1st-Year University Students	Buote, Pancer et al. (2007) [4]	University	702 students	Canada, North America	qualitative and quantitative	Results indicated a significant positive relation between quality of new friendships and adjustment to university; this association was stronger for students living in residence than for those commuting to university.
24	The Transition To University: Adaptation And Adjustment	Smith (2008) [24]	University	229 students	Canada, North America	Quantitative	During the first semester, easier transitions and better adjustment were largely predicted by more

							adaptive coping, good social support, better grades and fewer daily hassles. For women, second semester transition experiences and adjustment measures were strongly predicted by the same measures as observed in the first semester.
25	Friendsickness in the Transition to College: Precollege Predictors and College Adjustment Correlates	Paul and Brier (2001) [17]	University	70 students	USA	Quantitative	The results of the present study suggest that students who are highly preoccupied with and concerned about their precollege friendships exhibit poorer adjustment to college along a number of dimensions
26	Homesickness in Socially anxious first year college students	Urani, Miller et al. (2003) [30]	University	105 students	USA	Quantitative	the result indicated that the transition to university life can be very stressfull for the student, resulting in homesickness, and psychological disturbance
27	Social Class and Belonging: Implications for College Adjustment	Ostrove and Long (2007) [16]	University	252 students	USA	Quantitative	Both objective and subjective class background were significantly related to sense of belonging and to academic adjustment; subjective class background was also significantly related to social adjustment, and objective SES background was weakly correlated with GPA
28	The Role of Organized Activities in Facilitating Social	Bohnert, Aikins et al. (2007) [3]	University	85 adolescents	USA	Quantitative	These findings also suggest that the relation between change in best friendships and activity

	Adaptation Across the Transition to College						involvement in emerging adulthood may be mediated by social motivations.
29	Student Dormitory as a Character-Based Education in Higher Schools (A Case Study at Telkom University Dormitory – Bandung)	Murdowo, Budimansyah et al. (2017) [14]	University	30 students	Indonesia	Qualitative	Dormitory’s supervision and activity developed the aspects of adaptive, spiritual, academic and social (ASAS); assessment method to gain Student Activity Transcript point or Transkrip Aktivitas Mahasiswa (TAK) point; well-organized policy and program on the level of institution, supervision, and program organizer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section reports the main findings of the articles reviewed. The analysis shows that most articles focus on successful transitions and adjustments beginning when students first come into contact with college. Almost all studies show that freshmen are less mature emotionally, and have difficulty adjusting emotionally and socially to the demands of a changing environment. Many international studies on the transition to college highlight the importance of the transition period, research findings suggest that first-year freshmen may have adjustment problems and experience unwanted stress and psychological problems during the first-year on campus (Hicks and Heastie 2008). The sense of belonging to a college and the quality of friendships have a positive influence on adjustment and transition in college (Pittman and Richmond 2008). Therefore, it is important to help students, especially first year students, identify various coping strategies to deal with stress during their transition to college (Abdullah, Elias et al. 2010) one of which is through the boarding program.

For students who live in dormitories, they consider dormitories an important part of a better campus life, because they spend most of their time on campus. As a place to rest, learn and interact, dormitories are a vital place for the quality of student life. Directly, dormitories can develop adaptive, spiritual, academic and social aspects (Murdowo, Budimansyah et al. 2017). From the writer’s point of view, a good dorm life includes the following aspects: first, the residents of the hostel feel safe, which provides the foundation for a good dorm life because safety is the top priority in every place. Second, the hostel provides a clean and tidy environment. Third, the atmosphere is comfortable and pleasant in the dormitory because the hostel is like a house that provides warmth and comfort for its members. Fourth, dormitory residents enjoy a healthy lifestyle and are willing to face challenges that can improve themselves through activities in the dormitory.

In general, it can be concluded that the dormitory can play a key role in helping new students to overcome the problems of adjustment and transition through the program services in the hostel.

Like other studies, this review has limitations. First, the review of articles is only in Indonesian and English so that other studies are not reviewed due to the limitations of the author. Second, the scope of the articles reviewed is still very limited, in this paper the scope is only limited to research conducted in some countries in the Americas and some countries in the Asian continent, while the variations in the countries of the Americas and Asia that are reviewed are still lacking. A final limitation is that no single measure can be compared between studies. This review is still minimal and even challenging to find a lot of literature that combines the

variables of dormitory role, transition period and adjustment of first year students. The next step that needs to be done is a follow-up study (other research) - related to research on the role of dormitories in the transition and adjustment period of first-year students.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullah, M. C., et al. (2010). "Relationship between coping and university adjustment and academic achievement amongst first year undergraduates in a Malaysian public university." *International Journal of Arts and Sciences* 3(11): 379-392.
2. Berzonsky, M. D. and L. S. Kuk (2000). "Identity status, identity processing style, and the transition to university." *Journal of adolescent research* 15(1): 81-98.
3. Bohnert, A. M., et al. (2007). "The role of organized activities in facilitating social adaptation across the transition to college." *Journal of adolescent research* 22(2): 189-208.
4. Buote, V. M., et al. (2007). "The importance of friends: Friendship and adjustment among 1st-year university students." *Journal of adolescent research* 22(6): 665-689.
5. Dan-Ping, W. (2018). "Consultation, Contribution and Shared Benefits—The Golden Principle of Creating a Better Dormitory Life for College Students." *DEStech Transactions on Economics, Business and Management* (eced).
6. Elias, H., et al. (2010). "Achievement motivation and self-efficacy in relation to adjustment among university students." *Journal of social sciences* 6(3): 333-339.
7. Estiane, U. (2015). "Pengaruh dukungan sosial sahabat terhadap penyesuaian sosial mahasiswa baru di lingkungan perguruan tinggi." *Jurnal Psikologi Klinis dan Kesehatan Mental* 4(1): 29-40.
8. Friedlander, L. J., et al. (2007). "Social support, self-esteem, and stress as predictors of adjustment to university among first-year undergraduates." *Journal of college student development* 48(3): 259-274.
9. Fromme, K., et al. (2008). "Behavioral risks during the transition from high school to college." *Developmental psychology* 44(5): 1497.
10. Hicks, T. and S. Heastie (2008). "High school to college transition: A profile of the stressors, physical and psychological health issues that affect the first-year on-campus college student."
11. Hurtado, S., et al. (2007). "Predicting transition and adjustment to college: Biomedical and behavioral science aspirants' and minority students' first year of college." *Research in Higher education* 48(7): 841-887.
12. Inkelas, K. K., et al. (2007). "Living-learning programs and first-generation college students' academic and social transition to college." *Research in Higher education* 48(4): 403-434.
13. Mehdinezhad, V. (2011). "First Year Students' Engagement at the University." *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences* 3(1).
14. Murdowo, D., et al. (2017). "Student Dormitory as a Character-Based Education in Higher Schools (A Case Study at Telkom University Dormitory-Bandung)."
15. Murray, J. and P. Arajuo (2010). Estimating the Effects of Dormitory Living on Student Performance. Proceeding of the 2009 Southern Economics Conference, cited in Pat-Mbano, EC, Alaka, IN, and Okeoma, IO (2012), "Examining the Physio, psycho, and socioeconomic implications of non residency policy on Imo State University Students", Canadian Social Sciences.
16. Ostrove, J. M. and S. M. Long (2007). "Social class and belonging: Implications for college adjustment." *The Review of Higher Education* 30(4): 363-389.
17. Paul, E. L. and S. Brier (2001). "Friendsickness in the transition to college: Precollege predictors and college adjustment correlates." *Journal of Counseling & Development* 79(1): 77-89.
18. Pertiwi, D. A. (2017). "Implementasi Program Pendidikan Asrama Dalam Meningkatkan Kecerdasan Spiritual Santriwati Di Asrama Bahasa Arab Hubbul Wathan Medan." *At-Tazakki: Jurnal Kajian Ilmu Pendidikan Islam dan Humaniora* 1(2): 101-121.
19. Pittman, L. D. and A. Richmond (2008). "University belonging, friendship quality, and psychological adjustment during the transition to college." *The Journal of Experimental Education* 76(4): 343-362.
20. Rahat, E. and T. İlhan (2016). "Coping styles, social support, relational self-construal, and resilience in predicting students' adjustment to university life." *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice* 16(1).

21. Rodger, S. C. and A. W. Johnson (2005). "The Impact of Residence Design on Freshman Outcomes: Dormitories Versus Suite-Style Residences." *Canadian Journal of Higher Education* 35(3): 83-99.
22. Saffarpour, S., et al. (2011). "The effectiveness of solution-focused brief therapy on increasing social adjustment of female students residing in Tehran University dormitories." *International Journal of Psychology and Counselling* 3(2): 24-28.
23. Sharma, B. (2012). "Adjustment and emotional maturity among first year college students." *Pakistan Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology* 9(3): 32-37.
24. Smith, M. L. (2008). The transition to university: Adaptation and adjustment.
25. Souza, M. T. d., et al. (2010). "Integrative review: what is it? How to do it?" *Einstein (São Paulo)* 8(1): 102-106.
26. Tao, S., et al. (2000). "Social support: Relations to coping and adjustment during the transition to university in the People's Republic of China." *Journal of adolescent research* 15(1): 123-144.
27. Taylor, Z. E., et al. (2014). "Transitioning from high school to college: Relations of social support, ego-resiliency, and maladjustment during emerging adulthood." *Emerging Adulthood* 2(2): 105-115.
28. Thurber, C. A. and E. A. Walton (2012). "Homesickness and adjustment in university students." *Journal of American college health* 60(5): 415-419.
29. Torracco, R. J. (2005). "Writing integrative literature reviews: Guidelines and examples." *Human resource development review* 4(3): 356-367.
30. Urani, M. A., et al. (2003). "Homesickness in Socially-Anxious First Year College Students." *College Student Journal* 37(3): 392-399.
31. Utari, R., et al. (2014). "Pembentukan Iklim Sosial-akademik Di Asrama Mahasiswa." *Jurnal Penelitian Humaniora* 19(1).
32. Wintre, M. G. and M. Yaffe (2000). "First-year students' adjustment to university life as a function of relationships with parents." *Journal of adolescent research* 15(1): 9-37.

Cite this Article: Mukhroni, Sowiyah Sowiyah, Hasan Hariri (2021). Transition and Adjustment of First-Year Student College in Dormitory: A Literature Review. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 4(8), 895-905